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S3E CHARGE ACCELERATOR PROGRAM

MEET THE 12 SELECTED **STARTUPS**

FROM **SOUTHERN EUROPE**

THE ENGINE FOR **SOUTH EUROPEAN DEEP TECH**

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AUTOMATIC SOFTWARE DEVELOPMENT COSTS PROJECTIONS

Estimating software development costs is challenging. Technical debt is a crucial factor that tends to be overlooked, which gradually slows down development to the point where introducing new features becomes technically or financially unfeasible. Arcan is a SaaS B2B tool for companies developing and purchasing software that takes technical debt into account to accurately estimate software maintenance costs.

TEAM

Ilaria Pigazzini
CEO

Darius Sas
CTO

Davide Fanale
Business Dev Manager

SOLUTION

SaaS tool to forecast the true costs of software development, taking into account technical debt

TECH

AI (machine learning models, GPT, graph theory)

SECTOR

Enterprise Software

INVESTMENT NEEDED € 1.000.000

arcan.tech

HIGH QUALITY WATER PRODUCTION BY EFFICIENT DESALINATION

Fresh Water Nature has developed the Cool Steam system to transform fresh water production for Green Hydrogen generation. We use energy efficient modules to distill water at low temperatures, producing 5 times more water than electrolyzers need. The result? A high-quality pure water, suitable for sustainable and cost-effective hydrogen generation.

TEAM

Naeria Navarro
Technical Director

Javier Soraluca
R&D Engineer

SOLUTION

Ultra pure water supply for electrolysis in Green Hydrogen production

TECH

Vacuum distillation & electrolyzers

SECTOR

Water technologies

INVESTMENT NEEDED € 500.000

freshwaturnature.com

DECODING MENTAL HEALTH ONE WORD AT A TIME

Psychomeasure© is a clinical tool based on natural language processing (NLP) to support physicians in their diagnosis and monitoring of patients with schizophrenia. The traditional psychiatric diagnosis process is lengthy, subjective, and prone to errors. By using NLP technology, our product can significantly decrease the time of evaluation and diagnosis, adding precision and accuracy.

TEAM

Eduardo Barros
CEO

Renata Morais
Chief Innovation Officer

Gilson Schwartz
Scientific Advisor

SOLUTION

Deliver faster and more accurate diagnosis and monitoring for schizophrenia patients

TECH

Natural Language Processing (NLP), Graph Theory and Machine Learning

SECTOR

MedTech / Mental Health & Wellbeing

INVESTMENT NEEDED € 500.000 - € 1.000.000

psychomeasure.com

HELPING PEOPLE DECRYPT THEIR METABOLISM

ThetaBiomarkers is an innovative and technologically advanced research clinical laboratory offering metabolomics-based services for health, wellness and lifestyle purposes. Thanks to our biological sample analysis capabilities, our users receive accurate and meaningful results that allows them to make informed decisions for future treatment based on their metabolism data.

TEAM

Olga Begou
CEO

Georgios Theodoridis
CTO

SOLUTION

Effective and accurate quantification of biomarkers for health, wellness and lifestyle

TECH

Hyphenated mass spectrometry for metabolomics-based analysis

SECTOR

Healthtech / Biotech

INVESTMENT NEEDED € 600.000

thetabiomarkers.com

PHYSICAL PRODUCT RESEARCH IN VR ENVIRONMENTS

Digital Bites is a B2B platform that allows food companies to test their product concepts on their target audience before creating them. We use Virtual Reality to build environments where we can test, analyse and capture consumer behaviour and interaction with products. Our solutions helps consumer insights experts, marketing departments or NPD teams to validate new product concepts easily and rapidly.

TEAM

Theodoros Sofianos
CEO

Michael Tziortzis
CDO

Loukas Kakalis
CTO

SOLUTION

De-risk new product launches by offering accurate consumer feedback in pre-development stages

TECH

Virtual Reality for Behavioural Analysis and Neuromarketing

SECTOR

Enterprise Software / Food & Retail

INVESTMENT NEEDED € 400.000

digitalbites.eu

distinkt

SMART SECURITY INKS USING NANOTECHNOLOGY

We have created smart inks based on patented nanotechnology. They are used to create unique patterns, QR codes and holographic symbols for the purposes of anti-counterfeiting applications, thanks to color changing features as well as being dynamic and irreplicable. The technology is easily integrated into existing industrial printing processes, offering a very low-cost and time efficient integration system.

TEAM

Luca Venza
Co-founder & CEO

Àlex Julià López
Co-founder & CTO

SOLUTION

Nanotech-based security inks which are inexpensive, organic and impossible to copy

TECH

Chemistry + Nanotechnology

SECTOR

Chemical

INVESTMENT NEEDED

€ 2.000.000

distinkt.tech

DISRUPTIVE TECHNOLOGY FOR GREEN HYDROGEN PRODUCTION

Water2kW is the team behind H2umidity®, a sustainable and innovative system capable of producing Green Hydrogen and renewable electricity in conditions where water is scarce. H2umidity® provides the total use of the process by-products using advanced recovery systems. Using environmental humidity as a water source, we can contribute to the progress and development of regions that currently do not have easy or direct access to water or electricity.

TEAM

Juan Suárez
Founder & CEO

Luisa Fraga
R+D Manager

Perrine Nantois
R+D Engineer

Javier Rodríguez
R+D Engineer

SOLUTION

Producing green hydrogen by water electrolysis using only environmental humidity

TECH

Green hydrogen electrolysis (H2umidity®)

SECTOR

Sustainable and green energy

INVESTMENT NEEDED

€ 1.500.000 - € 2.000.000

water2kw.com

HELPING BUSINESSES LISTEN TO THEIR CUSTOMERS' NEEDS

IIO is an innovative Voice Platform for Customer Experience Management, based on the revolutionary combination of 3 AI-powered elements: our Adaptive Conversational Engine (ACE), human emotion recognition technology and generative AI. By leveraging advanced AI engines, our platform creates speech interactions, quickly learning and elaborating relevant responses in any language.

TEAM

Pasquale Bombino
Founder & CEO

SOLUTION

Delivering intelligent, emotionally aware and highly personalised CRM training experiences

TECH

Generative AI, Machine Learning & Natural Language Processing (NLP)

SECTOR

Customer Relationship Management

INVESTMENT NEEDED € 1.500.000

iio.tech

WE ROCKET YOUR ENERGY SAVINGS!

Our c-BEMS is a unique cloud-based and self-learning/adjusting SaaS tool for Building Energy Management System. It supports multi-zonal control of heating/cooling and lighting systems, providing energy savings of 40% on average in public and private buildings. Inteligg's c-BEMS also reduces installation expenses significantly, as buildings only need an internet connection to create a wireless local network for the devices to run on.

TEAM

Christos Ioakeimidis
CEO & Co-founder

Iakovos Poulis
Software Engineer

SOLUTION

Fixing energy inefficiency on buildings to cut down CO2 emissions contributing to climate change

TECH

Wireless and cloud tech, IoT, AI & Machine Learning

SECTOR

Construction / Climate Tech

INVESTMENT NEEDED

€ 900.000

inteligg.com

AN OCEAN OF GOOD TASTE

Bluana is a pioneering startup revolutionising the plant-based food industry by offering a sustainable and environmentally friendly seafood alternatives. Our unique and proprietary technology allows us to develop a new type of fish substitute that addresses several pressing challenges in the seafood industry, such as overfishing and the destruction of marine ecosystems.

TEAM

Florin Irimescu
CEO

Marco Iotti
CTO & Technical Lead

Anamaria Stan
Head Chef

SOLUTION

Tackle the environmental impact of the fishing industry by producing plant-based seafood

TECH

High Moisture & High Nutrients Injection

SECTOR

Food Tech

INVESTMENT NEEDED € 3.500.000

bluana.me

HARNESSING WIND POWER FOR GREEN ENERGY INNOVATION

With energy prices reaching record levels globally, Grawindy have developed an innovative wind-based green energy system capable of generating low-cost electricity. Compared to existing wind turbines, Grawindy uses recyclable materials to produce their equipment, contributing to decreasing the carbon footprint of electricity production while keeping costs at bay.

TEAM

Atilla Öztürk
CEO

SOLUTION

Turbine technology capable of operating in low wind speeds (3 m/s)

TECH

Wind turbines for renewable energy production

SECTOR

AgriTech

INVESTMENT NEEDED € 435.000

grawindy.com

LIVING HEALTHY WITH ASTHMA

AsthmaFit is an intelligent asthma management system consisting of a novel wearable device, an App and advanced AI-based software. AsthmaFit follows a data-based approach monitoring exposure, symptoms and activity, capable of tracking individuals' exposure to pollutants and gases as well as the location, duration and intensity of physical activity.

TEAM

Christos Spagkakas
CEO & Co-founder

Aleck Alexopoulos
CTO & Co-founder

SOLUTION

Providing an effective and personalised tool for asthma management to avoid hospitalisation

TECH

Wearable tech, Mobile application & AI-based software

SECTOR

Health Tech

INVESTMENT NEEDED € 300.000

respibit.com

THE ENGINE FOR **SOUTH EUROPEAN DEEP TECH**

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